

EFFICACY OF A LOCALLY MODIFIED DEL NIDO CARDIOPLEGIC SOLUTION BASED ON NORMAL SALINE IN PEDIATRIC CARDIAC SURGERY

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Abstract. *Effective myocardial protection remains a cornerstone of successful pediatric cardiac surgery. The choice of cardioplegia technique can significantly impact the extent of ischemia-reperfusion injury, particularly in young children with immature myocardium undergoing repair of congenital heart defects (CHDs). To compare the incidence of postoperative myocardial ischemic injury in children aged 1 to 3 years undergoing surgical correction of septal CHDs, based on the type of cardioplegic solution used: crystalloid versus blood-based modified del Nido solution. A prospective comparative study was conducted at the National Children's Medical Center (Uzbekistan) from February 2021 to December 2024. Ninety-one patients with ASD or VSD were randomized into two groups: the control group (n = 44) received cold crystalloid cardioplegia, and the intervention group (n = 57) received a locally modified del Nido solution supplemented with oxygenated blood (4:1 ratio). The primary endpoint was defined as a >10-fold increase in troponin I levels at 6 hours postoperatively, persisting at 24 hours. Secondary outcomes included changes in left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) and inotropic support requirements. The incidence of the primary endpoint was significantly lower in the del Nido group (31.3%) compared to the crystalloid group (62.5%; p < 0.001). While troponin I levels decreased over time in both groups, LVEF declined more substantially in the crystalloid group (30.7% vs. 18% reduction at 24 hours postoperatively). Blood-based del Nido cardioplegia provided superior myocardial protection compared to crystalloid cardioplegia in young children undergoing open-heart repair of septal defects, as evidenced by lower biomarker elevation and better preservation of ventricular function.*

Keywords: *cardioplegia, congenital heart defect, del Nido, cardiopulmonary bypass, pediatric cardiac surgery.*

Introduction. The issue of intraoperative myocardial protection against ischemic injury remains a subject of ongoing debate in modern cardiac surgery. This is evidenced by the wide variety of cardioplegic solutions and their numerous modifications currently in use. As the duration and complexity of cardiac procedures increase, so does the time under cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB) and myocardial ischemia, necessitating the development of more effective cardioplegic formulations for myocardial perfusion during the period of asystole [1, 2].

Ensuring adequate myocardial protection intraoperatively is a critical determinant of both immediate and long-term outcomes in congenital heart defect (CHD) correction [2, 3]. At present, 84.3% of cardiac surgeons prefer to perform open-heart procedures under cardioplegic arrest, with only 15.7% operating on fibrillating hearts. Among those using cardioplegia, 83.5% employ blood-based cardioplegia, while only 16.5% utilize crystalloid solutions [4]. Furthermore, according to Jacob S. (2008), 56% of surgeons preferred cold blood cardioplegia, 14% normothermic blood

cardioplegia, 14% crystalloid cardioplegia, 21% used retrograde delivery, and 16% did not use cardioplegia at all [5].

In the early 1990s, researchers at the University of Pittsburgh developed a cardioplegic solution tailored to the unique physiological needs of the immature myocardium. Their focus was on addressing intracellular calcium handling, preservation of high-energy phosphates, reduction of lactate production, and enhancement of intracellular buffering capacity. Dr. Pedro del Nido later modified the solution specifically for pediatric myocardial protection. However, its original base, Plasma-Lyte A, is not readily available in several Asian countries, including Uzbekistan.

In this study, a locally adapted formulation based on 0.9% normal saline and pharmacological agents in varying concentrations was used. Literature analysis has revealed a paucity of data correlating elevated cardiac troponin levels with echocardiographic (ECHO) parameters as indicators of myocardial injury [6, 7, 8]. Therefore, this study aims to comprehensively assess the efficacy of myocardial protection by analyzing metabolic indicators (CK-MB, troponin, lactate, glucose), CPB duration, aortic cross-clamp time, cardioplegia duration, incidence of ventricular fibrillation, need for inotropic support, duration of mechanical ventilation, and length of stay in the intensive care unit (ICU).

Study Objective. To evaluate and quantify the incidence of myocardial ischemic injury during open-heart surgery in young children with congenital heart defects, in relation to the cardioplegia method applied.

Materials and Methods. A prospective comparative study was conducted to evaluate the efficacy of intraoperative myocardial protection in young children (n = 101, aged 1 to 3 years) with congenital heart defects (CHDs) using either crystalloid or blood-based cardioplegia according to the del Nido protocol. The study was carried out at the National Children's Medical Center (Republic of Uzbekistan) between February 2021 and December 2024.

The study population included patients with septal CHDs—atrial septal defect (ASD) and ventricular septal defect (VSD)—who underwent elective open-heart surgery with cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB) and cardioplegic arrest. The patients were stratified into two groups:

- **Control group (n = 44):** received pharmacologically induced cold crystalloid cardioplegia.
- **Intervention group (n = 57):** received a locally modified del Nido solution with oxygenated blood added in a 4:1 solution-to-blood ratio.

Inclusion criteria:

- Children aged 1 to 3 years;
- Primary radical repair of isolated ASD or VSD;
- High-sensitivity troponin I (hs-TnI) level ≤ 0.034 ng/mL;
- No ischemic changes on ECG;
- Absence of concomitant or hereditary pathology;
- Informed consent obtained from parents or legal guardians.

Exclusion criteria:

- Prior palliative surgery for CHD;
- Presence of other types of CHDs;
- Lack of informed consent from the child's legal representative.

All patients received standardized general anesthesia using conventional induction and maintenance agents. The surgical approach consisted of a median sternotomy, preparation of an autologous pericardial patch, and initiation of CPB via cannulation of the ascending aorta and bicaval venous cannulation of the superior and inferior vena cava.

Cardiac arrest was achieved via antegrade delivery of the cardioplegic solution through an aortic root cannula after aortic cross-clamping, at a target body temperature of 32–33°C. Cardioplegia solutions were prepared by nursing staff following a pre-defined digital protocol, observing strict aseptic technique, and cooled to a temperature of 2–4°C. In the del Nido group, oxygenated blood was added to the solution following the initiation of CPB.

After restoration of spontaneous cardiac activity and weaning from CPB, all patients underwent modified ultrafiltration. The compositions of the cardioplegic solutions used in both groups are detailed in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Original Del Nido Cardioplegia Formulation

Ingredient	Volume (mL)	Function
Plasma-Lyte A	1000.0	Base solution: Na 140 mEq/L; K 5 mEq/L; Mg 3 mEq/L; pH 7.4
Potassium chloride (KCl)	13.0	Myocardial depolarization
Sodium bicarbonate 8.4% (NaHCO ₃)	13.0	pH buffer
Magnesium sulfate 50% (MgSO ₄)	4.0	Calcium channel blocker, enhances myocardial recovery
Lidocaine 1%	13.0	Sodium channel blocker, hyperpolarizing agent
Mannitol 20%	16.3	Osmotic agent, scavenger of free radicals

Table 2. Composition of Cardioplegic Solutions Used in the Study

Ingredient	Crystalloid Cardioplegia (CC)	Modified del Nido Solution	Function
Sodium chloride 0.9% (NaCl)	500.0 mL	500.0 mL	Base solution
Potassium chloride 4% (KCl)	32.5 mL	32.6 mL	Myocardial depolarization
Sodium bicarbonate 4% (NaHCO ₃)	13.8 mL	14.4 mL	pH buffer
Magnesium sulfate 25%	4.0 mL	4.2 mL	Calcium channel blocker
Lidocaine 2%	3.25 mL	3.4 mL	Sodium channel blocker, stabilizes membrane potential
Mannitol 15%	11.5 mL	11.5 mL	Osmotic diuretic, free radical scavenger

Ingredient	Crystalloid Cardioplegia (CC)	Modified del Nido Solution	Function
Glucose 40%	2.5 mL	—	Energy substrate (present only in CC solution)
Oxygenated autologous blood	—	142.0 mL	Oxygen carrier, added in a 1:4 ratio (blood:solution)

We also developed a custom electronic calculator for cardioplegic solution formulation, which enables rapid and precise computation of the required drug volumes. This tool minimizes reagent overuse and allows for individualized volume adjustment based on the patient's body weight.

Table 3. Electronic Calculator for Modified Del Nido Cardioplegia Composition

Component	Concentration (mg/mL)	Volume (mL)
Sodium chloride 0.9%	7.947	200.0
Mannitol 15% (150 mg/mL)	3.044	4.6
Lidocaine 2% (20 mg/mL)	0.122	1.4
Magnesium sulfate 25% (250 mg/mL)	1.867	1.7
Sodium bicarbonate 4% (40 mg/mL)	1.020	5.8
Potassium chloride 4%	2.304	13.0
Mix the prepared volume by shaking 3 times	4 parts	226.5
Add oxygenated blood (mL)	1 part	57.0
Administer cold (6–8°C) at a dosage of 20 mL/kg, not exceeding 100 mmHg	Total: 5 parts	283.0

Specify volume of NaCl 0.9% for final solution preparation

Endpoints and Measurements

Primary endpoints included a >10-fold increase in troponin I levels at 6 hours postoperatively, persisting at 24 hours, and the confirmation of **myocardial injury syndrome**. This syndrome was defined by sustained elevation of troponin I levels (>10× the upper reference limit) at both 6 and 24 hours post-surgery, accompanied by the appearance of pathological Q waves, complete left bundle branch block (LBBB), and a ≥50% reduction in global longitudinal strain (GLS) of the left ventricle on transthoracic echocardiography (TTE) compared to preoperative values.

Cardiac biomarkers (troponin I and CK-MB) were measured using a high-sensitivity immunofluorescence method with Troponin I and CK-MB reagents and calibrators (NT-proBNP, Finecare) on the WONDFO Finecare III Plus analyzer. Measurements were obtained preoperatively, as well as 6 hours, 24 hours, and on postoperative day 3. Reference ranges:

- Troponin I: 0–0.1 ng/mL
- CK-MB: 0–5 ng/mL

Transthoracic echocardiography was performed using the Vivid T8 ultrasound system (General Electric Healthcare, USA) before surgery, and at 6 hours, 24 hours, and day 10

postoperatively. **Inotropic support** was administered as needed and quantified using the **vasoactive-inotropic score (VIS)**, calculated as follows:

$VIS = \text{dobutamine} + \text{dopamine} + \text{epinephrine} + (100 \times \text{norepinephrine}) + (10 \times \text{milrinone})$
 $VIS = \text{dobutamine} + \text{dopamine} + \text{epinephrine} + (100 \times \text{norepinephrine}) + (10 \times \text{milrinone})$ where all dosages are expressed in $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{min}$ [9].

Statistical analysis was performed using Statistica 13.5 software. For continuous variables, the paired Student's t-test was used to assess statistical significance. Categorical data were analyzed using Pearson's chi-squared (χ^2) test. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Table 4. Patient Characteristics and Clinical Parameters by Group

Parameter	Control Group (n = 44)	Del Nido Group (n = 57)	p-value
Sex (M/F), %	31 (77.5) / 9 (22.5)	40 (78.4) / 11 (21.6)	> 0.05
Age (months)	26 ± 1.9	20.3 ± 2.1	> 0.05
Body Mass Index (kg/m ²)	23.6 ± 1.5	25.9 ± 3.2	> 0.05
Body Surface Area (m ²)	0.52 ± 0.02	0.49 ± 0.04	> 0.05
VSD/ASD, %	82.5 / 17.5	80.4 / 19.6	> 0.05
Heart Rate (bpm)	129.3 ± 8.3	135.1 ± 7.5	—
CPB time (min)	62.0 ± 6.9	55.2 ± 5.4	—
Aortic cross-clamp time (min)	34.6 ± 3.0	31.8 ± 3.6	—
CPB time post-clamp release (min)	13.8 ± 2.0	9.5 ± 1.1	—
Total operation time (min)	176 ± 10.3	129 ± 8.7	—
Mechanical ventilation duration (hours)	21.1 ± 0.1	19.1 ± 0.1	—
ICU stay duration (hours)	48.7 ± 1.0	48.0 ± 0.1	—
Time to asystole induction (sec)	48.2 ± 5.0	40.3 ± 1.0	—
Repeat cardioplegia administration, %	36.3	6.6	—
Troponin I at 6 h post-op (ng/mL)	9.03 ± 1.02	7.09 ± 0.01	—
Troponin I at 24 h post-op (ng/mL)	7.99 ± 1.01	6.50 ± 0.71	—
CK-MB at 6 h post-op (ng/mL)	19.7 ± 1.00	15.3 ± 1.01	—
CK-MB at 24 h post-op (ng/mL)	16.7 ± 1.32	13.6 ± 1.00	—
Lactate pre-op (mmol/L)	1.00 ± 0.01	1.45 ± 0.02	—
Lactate at 2 h post-op (mmol/L)	1.27 ± 0.01	1.33 ± 0.00	—
Glucose before CPB (mmol/L)	5.10 ± 0.11	5.28 ± 0.11	—
Glucose during CPB (mmol/L)	8.47 ± 1.12	8.31 ± 1.03	—
Glucose after CPB (mmol/L)	12.3 ± 1.13	10.3 ± 1.23	—
Ejection Fraction (EF) pre-op (%)	66.8	66.3	—

Parameter	Control Group (n = 44)	Del Nido Group (n = 57)	p-value
EF at 24 h post-op (%)	46.5	54.4	—
EF at discharge (%)	55.3	62.7	—

Preoperative plasma troponin I concentrations were within the reference range in both study groups. Preoperative echocardiographic assessment showed no statistically significant differences in left ventricular longitudinal mechanics or other baseline cardiac parameters. Similarly, there were no significant intergroup differences in cardiopulmonary bypass duration, aortic cross-clamp time (myocardial ischemia), duration of mechanical ventilation, or length of stay in the intensive care unit (ICU). **No mortality** was recorded in either group.

The dynamics of **troponin I levels** revealed statistically significant differences between the groups. At 6 hours postoperatively, troponin I levels were elevated in all patients; however, levels were significantly higher in the **crystalloid cardioplegia group (CC)** compared to the **del Nido group** (9.03 vs. 7.09 ng/mL; $p < 0.001$).

In the **del Nido group**, 16 patients exhibited a >10-fold elevation in troponin I levels at 6 hours, persisting at 24 hours. In comparison, 25 patients in the **CC group** met this criterion. Thus, the **primary endpoint** was reached in:

- **28% (16/57)** of patients in the **del Nido group**, and
- **56.8% (25/44)** of patients in the **CC group** ($p < 0.001$).

Subsequent analysis showed a reduction in troponin I levels across both groups at later time points, with **no statistically significant differences** in the degree of reduction.

However, significant **intergroup differences in left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF)** were observed. At 24 hours postoperatively:

- LVEF in the **CC group** decreased by **30.7%** from baseline,
- LVEF in the **del Nido group** decreased by **18%**, indicating superior preservation of myocardial function in the latter.

Figure 1. Postoperative Troponin I Dynamics in the CC and Del Nido Groups

Additional Observations. No significant intergroup differences were observed in the dynamics of serum lactate and glucose levels at any postoperative stage. Furthermore, no cases of new-onset complete left bundle branch block (LBBB) or severe arrhythmias were detected in the postoperative period among patients in either group.

Discussion. This study compared two commonly used cardioplegic strategies for the surgical correction of ventricular and atrial septal defects in children: conventional crystalloid cardioplegia and modified blood-based del Nido cardioplegia.

Patients in the **del Nido group** demonstrated:

- lower postoperative elevations in **troponin I**,
- better preservation of **left ventricular longitudinal mechanics**,
- and required **less intensive inotropic support** compared to those in the crystalloid group.

Currently, the literature offers **no consensus** regarding the optimal cardioplegic strategy for pediatric patients [10, 11]. Dynamic measurement of **troponin I** has been proposed as a sensitive marker for intraoperative myocardial injury, including in children [12]. However, **there are no established pediatric-specific thresholds** for the prognostic interpretation of troponin I levels following surgical repair of congenital heart defects.

A recent study by **J.A. Su et al. (2019)** reported that troponin I was elevated in 93% of infants under one year of age at 8 hours postoperatively following CHD repair. However, only 14% demonstrated **persistent or rising levels** beyond this time point. These patients experienced various **hypoperfusion-related complications**, including **low cardiac output syndrome, stroke, and acute kidney injury** during the early postoperative period.

The study did not establish a definitive cutoff value for predicting such events, although a troponin I level of **8.44 ng/mL at 12 hours** showed a **trend toward prognostic relevance** ($p = 0.1$, AUC = 0.53) [12].

In our study, **21 patients (23.07%)** exhibited persistently elevated troponin I levels at 24 hours postoperatively, which was accompanied by **ECG changes** and increased inotropic requirements. These patients were diagnosed with **myocardial injury syndrome**, most likely resulting from a combination of **surgical myocardial trauma and adverse effects of cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB)**.

Conclusion. Myocardial injury syndrome was **identified in 26%** of cases **during the early postoperative period following surgical correction of ventricular and atrial septal defects in young children. This syndrome was characterized by** persistent elevation of troponin I levels (**>24 hours**), ischemic changes on ECG, **and a need for intensified inotropic support.**

1. In this patient population, the use of **blood-based del Nido cardioplegia** was associated with **reduced incidence and severity of postoperative myocardial injury** compared to pharmacologically induced cold crystalloid cardioplegia, indicating a potential advantage of the del Nido technique in pediatric congenital heart surgery.

REFERENCES

1. Petrishchev YA, Levit AL. Effect of the temperature regime of artificial blood circulation on oxygen transport. *Intensive Therapy*. 2006;(4):101–104. [In Russian]

2. Drury NE, Yim I, Patel A, et al. Cardioplegia in paediatric cardiac surgery: A systematic review of randomized controlled trials. *Interact Cardiovasc Thorac Surg*. 2019;28(1):144–150.
3. Adan A, Eleyan L, Zaidi M, et al. Ventricular septal defect: diagnosis and treatments in neonates—a systematic review. *Cardiol Young*. 2021;31(5):756–761. doi:10.1017/S1047951120004576
4. Karthik S, Grayson AD, Fabri BM. A survey of current myocardial protection practices during coronary artery bypass grafting. *Ann R Coll Surg Engl*. 2004;86:413–415.
5. Jacob S. Is blood cardioplegia superior to crystalloid cardioplegia? *Interact Cardiovasc Thorac Surg*. 2008;7(3):491–498.
6. Devereaux PJ, Lamy A, Chan MTV, et al; VISION Cardiac Surgery Investigators. High-sensitivity troponin I after cardiac surgery and 30-day mortality. *N Engl J Med*. 2022;386(9):827–836. doi:10.1056/NEJMoa2000803
7. Kotby AA, Abd Al Aziz MM, Hussein AH, Al-Fahham MM. Detection of early myocardial injury in children with ventricular septal defect using cardiac troponin I and two-dimensional speckle tracking echocardiography. *Pediatr Cardiol*. 2020;41(8):1548–1558. doi:10.1007/s00246-020-02410-2
8. Aly D, Madan N, Kuzava L, Samrany A, Parthiban A. Comprehensive evaluation of left ventricular deformation using speckle tracking echocardiography in normal children: comparison of 3D and 2D approaches. *Cardiovasc Ultrasound*. 2022;20(1):3. doi:10.1186/s12947-022-00273-6
9. Gaies MG, Jeffries HE, Niebler RA, et al. Vasoactive-inotropic score is associated with outcome after infant cardiac surgery: an analysis from the Pediatric Cardiac Critical Care Consortium and Virtual PICU System Registries. *Pediatr Crit Care Med*. 2014;15(6):529–537. doi:10.1097/PCC.0000000000000153
10. Uglova EV, Nartsissova GP, Kniazkova LG, et al. Clinical and biochemical aspects of myocardium protection efficiency during major surgery for congenital heart diseases in infants. *Circulation Pathology and Cardiac Surgery*. 2011;(1):41–48. [In Russian]
11. Uglova EV, Larionov PM, Lomivorotov VN, et al. Comparative assessment of myocardium protection methods with analysis of DNA damage in cardiomyocytes in infants. *Circulation Pathology and Cardiac Surgery*. 2009;(2):30–33. [In Russian]
12. Su JA, Kumar SR, Mahmoud H, et al. Postoperative serum troponin trends in infants undergoing cardiac surgery. *Semin Thorac Cardiovasc Surg*. 2019;31(2):244–251. doi:10.1053/j.semtcvs.2018.08.010